

1 **Climate Services Ecosystems: more bang for the bucks**

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11 ABSTRACT: During the last decade climate services have been exponentially proliferating in
12 number and diversity. Without the profound understanding, coordination and synergies among the
13 different climate services present in a particular country, society can miss opportunities to increase
14 resilience to climate impacts, or -what is worse- the number and diversity of disconnected climate
15 services available to stakeholders can delay, freeze or even dismantle ongoing adaptation strategies
16 and action plans. Building healthy ecosystems of climate services is a way to guarantee that society
17 enhances resilience, while optimally orchestrating the available resources. These ecosystems tend
18 to be more robust to climate impacts than a collection of climate services focused on certain
19 applications or just one sector, because shocks to one part of the ecosystem are redistributed and
20 dampened through the entire network. The paper describes the concept and elements of climate
21 services ecosystems and introduces the use of Network Analysis and Dynamic Causal Network
22 Theory to compare ecosystems of climate services. It further assess what are the most efficient
23 network configurations to efficiently communicate and use climate information produced by the
24 different actors in the ecosystem. This approach provides an objective way to assess potential or
25 actual causal relationships between their elements, the dynamics of their interactions and the value
26 of the ecosystem. The climate services ecosystem approach assesses the value of an integrated
27 collection of climate services, under scenarios of a changing climate, changes of societal needs and
28 limited budgets, supporting stakeholders to define what, when and how to fund climate services.

29 SIGNIFICANCE STATEMENT: The purpose of the paper is to propose a new way to analyze
30 climate services, from an ecosystem perspective, rather than disconnected one-sector-only services.
31 Ecosystems of climate services tend to be more robust to impacts than a collection of individual
32 climate services, because the shocks to one part of the ecosystem are re-distributed through the
33 network, making communities more resilient to shocks. The approaches discussed in this paper
34 will allow to understand how information (or budget) flow circulates in climate services ecosystem,
35 what are the most efficient network configurations to efficiently communicate and use climate
36 information produced by the different actors in the ecosystem, and to estimate impact of past
37 and future changes, following a story-line approach. This system thinking approach presents also
38 contributes to the discussion around the scalability of climate services within the community.

39 **1. Introduction**

40 Climate services have been proliferating in the past decades among developed and developing
41 communities (Vaughan and Dessai 2014; Buontempo et al. 2014; Hansen et al. 2014; Euro-
42 peanCommission et al. 2015; Goddard 2016; Brasseur and Gallardo 2016; Larosa and Mysiak
43 2019; Visscher et al. 2019; Hewitt et al. 2020; Goddard et al. 2020; Hewitt and Stone 2021)
44 as societies are using climate services to support their adaptation and mitigation strategies to
45 a changing climate (e.g. Cortekar et al. 2016; Scott et al. 2011). However, there is a lack of
46 agreement around the definition of the term, how to tackle scalability issues and the need for
47 standardization within its own community. This lack of understanding also impacts the attribution
48 of value to climate services and their implications for society in general (WMO 2015), limit-
49 ing the optimal development of these types of services for both, adaptation and mitigation purposes.

50
51 By definition, climate services require for climate data and climate information (or knowl-
52 edge) to be co-developed, translated, communicated and used (Hewitt and Stone 2021; Lemos
53 et al. 2018; Goddard 2016; Vaughan and Dessai 2014). At the centre of this definition of climate
54 services lays the concepts of usability and the use of a demand-driven approach. This approach
55 requires continuous collaboration and communication between stakeholders, including final
56 users, scientists and services providers (Baulenas et al. 2023; Lourenço et al. 2016) with the
57 objective to provide science-informed or local knowledge-informed value-based outcomes for the

58 decision-making process of particular users or communities.

59
60 The concept of climate services as an outcome of the co-development process described in
61 the previous paragraph does not happen in a linear process, but rather in a complex, dynamic and
62 multi-dimensional fashion (Guentchev et al. 2023). Several initiatives aim to smooth that process
63 through different pathways: the standardization of climate services Climateurope2¹, NOAA
64 strategic Plan², Climate Ready Nation Initiative and Equitable Climate Service Action Plan³,
65 the embedding of climate services into policy, UK Climate Resilience Programme⁴, Mission
66 Adaptation⁵, or the reduction of the usability gap through climate science innovation Horizon
67 Europe funded Impetus4Change⁶ and Horizon Europe funded ASPECT⁷ projects, just to mention
68 a few). Yet, different typologies and conceptualisations of climate services, along with data
69 constrains, the need for more tailored solutions, the lack of clear value in the climate services
70 market, poor monitoring and evaluation strategies, or funding issues, etc. constrains the capacity
71 to scale climate services and to use them as a mean to support society to prepare, cope and recover
72 from changes in climate.

73
74 Experimental approaches, demos, and pilot projects are a fundamental step in the produc-
75 tion chain of climate services. However, they can also present themselves as a limitation to upscale
76 and the democratise climate services. High level specialisation of pilots, a poor understanding
77 of what scalability is, and a lack of system thinking are some of the factors that have prevented
78 a functional upscale in the climate services arena (Guentchev et al. 2023; Hewitt et al. 2020;
79 Woltering et al. 2019). Other factors are related to biased collaboration, limited incentives to
80 scale and shielding from the real world (Woltering et al. 2019)- among others. The intregration of
81 climate services into a CSE, moving from a pilots and silos- climate services reality to a system
82 thinking, could support horizontal, vertical and functional upscaling processes, help with the
83 democratization of climate services and orchestrate resources within the CSE.

¹<http://climateurope2.eu>

²<https://www.noaa.gov/organization/budget-finance-performance/value-to-society/noaa-fy22-26-strategic-plan>

³<https://www.noaa.gov/sites/default/files/2024-04/NOAA-ECSAP-Final.pdf>

⁴<https://www.ukclimateresilience.org>

⁵<https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe>

⁶<https://impetus4change.eu/>

⁷<https://www.aspect-project.eu/>

84 This paper offers a new perspective on the definition of CSE, by analyzing the development,
 85 integration and value of climate services that are useful and beneficial for multiple sectors. Although
 86 there might be different ways to analyze CSEs, the authors define the term from a perspective of
 87 resources optimization, scalability and increased resilience. The concept also responds to the needs
 88 of the community to accrue the benefits of climate services for adaptation and mitigation purposes
 89 in a world with limited resources. The authors propose to use Network Analysis and Dynamic
 90 Causal Network Theory to analyze the interactions of the different climate services within a CSE.
 91 The overall purpose is to provide an objective tool to define CSEs, the observable associations and
 92 potential or actual causal relationships between their elements, the dynamics of their interactions
 93 and the value of the ecosystem.

FIG. 1. A simplified example comparing a climate service (left) and a climate service ecosystem (right).

94 **2. Defining Climate Services Ecosystems**

95 Traditionally, climate services have been defined and framed around a particular single
96 application or sector, either agriculture, health, energy, water management or disaster risk
97 management (Organization 2009; Council 2001)- just to mention a few. Whilst this approach
98 can bring potential benefits such as high specialisation, support for mitigation and adaptation
99 (Allis et al. 2019; Lemos 2015), co-benefits of articulated climate services among different sectors
100 have not been fully assessed in the broader societal system. Understanding and valuing the
101 nexus between sectors during the design, development and implementation of climate services
102 might help project optimization, the scalability of climate services and eventually benefits the
103 community, the country, an entire region or society through a higher resilience to changes in climate.

104
105 The current scene to obtain resources for climate services is more competitive than ever,
106 and donors and investors are more and more interested in demonstrating the value of climate
107 services, the return of their investments (Tall et al. 2018) and the capacity to scale up prototypes
108 of climate services. A first step to address these issues would be to define rules-of-the-game and
109 resources allocation for the orchestration of potential and actual climate services interacting in a
110 given space. Due to the similarities with the ecological definition, it has been proposed (Goddard
111 et al. 2020) to define that space of interactions as climate services ecosystems (CSEs). Following
112 the definition above of climate services, the first attempt to define climate services ecosystems was
113 recently proposed (GonzalezRomero et al. 2023; Goddard et al. 2020) as -slightly modifying the
114 business-perspective definition of Vargo and Akaka - “a relatively self-contained, self-adjusting
115 systems of resource-integrating actors connected by shared institutional goals, and mutual-value
116 creation through exchange of climate services” (Vargo and Akaka 2012).

117
118 Although the term climate services ecosystem is still a relatively new idea (GonzalezRomero
119 et al. 2023; Goddard et al. 2020), some predecessors of this concept have long been established.
120 In 2009, the World Climate Conference developed the Global Framework for Climate Services
121 (GFCS), a UN-led initiative coordinated by WMO to guide the development and application of
122 science-based climate information and services in support of decision-making in climate sensitive
123 sectors (Services 2023; WMO 2014; Hewitt et al. 2012). The original GFCS Implementation

124 Plan (WMO 2014, section 4.6.1) referenced what is now known as the National Framework for
125 Climate Services (NFCS), which aim to coordinate institutions at a national level and enable them
126 to work together to co-design, co-produce, communicate, deliver and use climate services for
127 decision-making in climate-sensitive socioeconomic sectors (WMO 2018). This co-production
128 among different institutions in a given country does not always happen horizontally across different
129 sectors; instead, climate services tend to be co-developed independently and sector-oriented.
130 The concept of climate service ecosystem brings the focus to the nexus between sectors and the
131 opportunity for optimization and increase resilience as a result of that nexus, completely aligned
132 with the goals of the NFCS and the GFCS.

133
134 In brief, a climate service ecosystem is a dynamic complex network of institutions, agents,
135 information, knowledge, products and services functioning as a unit, at any (or across multiple)
136 spatial or temporal scale(s), with the objective of supporting decision-making to enhance the
137 resilience to a changing climate, and support countries and institutions to achieve their adaptation
138 and mitigation goals while optimising available resources. Similarly to natural ecosystems,
139 climate services ecosystems are self-contained and self-adjusting, having the ability to adapt in
140 response to changes in the network or system (Begon and Townsend 2021; Chapin et al. 2011;
141 MilleniumEcosystemAssessment 2003). Ideally, the more interconnected and interdependent the
142 elements of the climate service ecosystem are, the higher the value and resilience of its network
143 (e.g. Sawai 2013; Watts and Strogatz 1998).

144
145 The characteristics of a CSE do not differ significantly from those for climate services. A
146 CSE needs to fit-for-purpose and provide tailored information in order to satisfy the demand of
147 its own ecosystem. It also needs to be flexible to be able to adapt to the dynamism of the needs
148 and the climate shocks and has to provide a continuous improvement approach through feedback
149 processes between climate services. In addition to these, the elements of a CSE are interdependent
150 of one another, present a mutual value creation through the establishment of shared goals and offer
151 transparency and traceability of the information flow.

152
153 To illustrate the ideas, Figure 1 shows a schematic and simplified representation of a cli-

154 mate service ecosystem involving both the agriculture and health sectors. Climate services for
155 these two sectors are usually developed in silos. The most frequent situation at the time of writing
156 this paper is that two different projects (and donors) work with different actors to co-produce two
157 different services. In this example, a plague forecast system is co-developed with a particular
158 farmer association, and a dengue forecast system is co-developed with the Ministry of Health. The
159 climate information required for these two systems is facilitated by a common provider, in this case
160 the National Meteorological Service. Because these two services share several common elements
161 (in this example, the nexus is a seasonal precipitation forecast system), it is possible to optimise
162 resources if the two separated services were part of an ecosystem of services, as discussed in the
163 following pages.

164
165 The ability of a CSE to fulfil its overall objective (to be “fit-for-purpose”) depends on the
166 relationship of its elements (interdependency). The use of Theory of Directed Graph in CSEs is of
167 particular value as it applies to structural, functional and effective connectivity and interactions.
168 Graphs are composed of nodes or vertices (corresponding to climate services) and edges
169 (corresponding to pathways, or dependencies between the elements of the graph).

170 The following subsections further explain in a qualitative way the relationship between
171 connectivity, interactions and resource optimization, and why these characteristics to analyse CSE
172 are relevant for analyzing the resilience capacity of a CSE in a context of economic constraints and
173 limited resources. These subsections are presented as proposals of “ideal attributes” of CSE, and
174 are based on results found in other related fields (e.g. Economics, Network Analysis, Ecology);
175 nonetheless, since each climate services ecosystem has its own peculiarities, they should be
176 considered hypothesis to be tested in each context, and not one-size-fits-all statements.

177

178 *a. Enhancing resilience depends on connectivity and interactions*

179 Climate services ecosystems involve interactions between different institutions, agents or sectors
180 sharing the same or similar climate services. As per the definition of climate services (Vaughan
181 and Dessai 2014; European Commission et al. 2015; Hewitt and Stone 2021) these interactions
182 require climate data, information or knowledge to be translated, shared, used and communicated

183 bidirectionally, allowing for feedback processes between users and providers of climate services
184 within the system. These interactions within the network aim to enhance its resilience, and
185 lends efficiency and value, by optimally orchestrating the available resources (Goddard et al. 2020).

186
187 In other words, CSE tend to be more robust to climate and socio-economic impacts than a
188 loose collection of climate services focused on a single sector, an idea aligned with well-
189 established results of previous studies analyzing stability and resilience in networks (e.g. Liu et al.
190 2022; Zhang et al. 2018; Watts and Strogatz 1998). In a CSE, the shock received by the ecosystem
191 is redistributed and dampened through part or the entire network. Interactions can also contain
192 functional redundancies (or repetition of climate services). Some of these repetitions may help to
193 keep the equilibrium of the ecosystem when dealing with changes or shocks impacting the network
194 (positive redundancies); however, other duplication of services may decrease the optimization of
195 resources.

196 *b. Efficient interactions optimise resources*

197 Another characteristic to consider when analysing these interactions is the level and efficiency
198 of the service contributing to the overall CSE. While some services or institutions make key
199 but sporadic contributions to the ecosystem dynamics, others tend to contribute more frequently
200 and more efficiently, in such a way that their disappearance would greatly affect the system
201 (MilleniumEcosystemAssessment 2003). Hence, identifying multiple configurations assigning
202 a balanced and efficient contribution to the different actors in the ecosystem is key. To analyse
203 comparative efficiency in climate services ecosystems, this paper proposes to apply the use of
204 Pareto efficiency (Iancu and Trichakis 2014). A Pareto-efficient CSE (cf. left and right sides of
205 Figure 2) implies that the allocation of climate services (and thus, resources) cannot be conducted
206 differently without making one institution or sector worse off.

207
208 For example, the left-hand side of Figure 2 exhibits a non-Pareto-efficient climate service
209 ecosystem, in which two institutions from different sectors replicate the same climate service- e.g.
210 a seasonal forecast system for precipitation. While a duplication of climate services sometimes is
211 necessary, in this case it results in a non-Pareto-efficient solution for the existing demand and thus,

212 a non-optimal use of resources within the ecosystem. This outcome could also result in increased
 213 mistrust in the forecasts themselves if or when they do not predict the same outcome.

214
 215 In contrast, a Pareto-improved CSE is shown on the right-hand side of Figure 2. There,
 216 the National Meteorological and Hydrological Service, the responsible governing body, issues a
 217 seasonal forecast for precipitation that is used by a farming association to develop an index-based
 218 insurance for its associated farmers. This new paradigm further promotes specialization,
 219 orchestration of resources and a higher resilience of the ecosystem.

FIG. 2. Optimisation of resources for Climate Services Ecosystems (CSE). (Left) A National Meteorological Service provides a seasonal forecast system for precipitation to the general public (dotted line), and -because of a funded project- provided observed rainfall data to a particular farming association, which used the data to internally produce a different seasonal precipitation forecast system for its farmers. (Right) A National Meteorological Service provides a seasonal forecast system for precipitation which uses additional information provided by the farming association (e.g. additional observed rainfall data from a private network). Since the farming association does not need to invest time and other resources to produce an internal seasonal forecast system, it is able to co-produce with an insurance company a tailored index-based insurance product.

221 As mentioned, there are cases in which duplicity of resources or services increases efficiency in a
 222 CSE. Figure 3 displays an example of such positive duplication. In this example, two institutions
 223 work together to develop a climate service; for simplicity, assume it is exactly the same seasonal
 224 precipitation forecast system. The forecast is directly communicated every month to stakeholders
 225 by the two institutions, and posted in each other's websites serving as a mirror or back-up option).
 226 In this case, the duplication allows for a continuation of the service in case that a shock impacts
 227 one of the institutions, such as a funding, leadership or any other change eliminating the service in
 one of the institutions.

FIG. 3. An example of positive duplication of services in a CSE

228

229 *c. Optimisation of resources adds value*

230 The concept of value has long been a philosophical question without a straightforward answer
 231 (Perry 1914). The utilitarian (or anthropocentric) definition of value, widely used in many
 232 disciplines, frames the paradigm of value on the principle of humans' preference satisfaction
 233 (MilleniumEcosystemAssessment 2003). This perspective is aligned with the user-centred

234 approach of climate services (Goddard et al. 2014; Goddard 2016; Buontempo et al. 2018; Goddard
235 et al. 2020; Lu et al. 2021)) –in contrast to the supply-centred one–, and it is also compatible with
236 the concept of *utility* in Economics e.g.(Growiec et al. 2018; Economides 1996).

237
238 Utility refers to the choices made by consumers –and usually limited by a given budget–
239 that increases their satisfaction or benefits and, in consequence, the value or worth of a given
240 product or service. The different possibilities of arrangements within a CSE and the different
241 country-specific needs, make it difficult to assess nor to assign a predetermine value to a CSE. The
242 definition of value of a CSE is thus determined by the satisfaction of the existing demand for that
243 particular ecosystem in a given point of time, which requires the co-design, co-development and
244 co-implementation of the climate services that compose the ecosystem.

245
246 The approach presented here links the concept of value of the CSE to the concepts of risk
247 and resilience. The more interconnected the CSE is, the higher the capacity to absorb the impact
248 of the climate shock is, and thus, the more resilient the system is. The term resilience has had
249 numerous definitions that have evolved over time (Alexander 2013). Here, the term resilience
250 refers to the state and capacity of an CSE to adapt and respond to different hazards, or crisis
251 under various probabilistic conditions (Haimes 2011, 2009). The resilience of the CSE is subject
252 to different state conditions established in a timely manner by the interactions and characteristic
253 of the network in that specific point of time. This makes the idea of value of the ecosystem a
254 dynamic concept based on the needs of the stakeholders, the conditions impacting the ecosystem
255 and the risks impacting the CSE. If either of those changes, the value of the ecosystem will
256 need to be reassessed and, more likely than not, it will offer a different value (or resilience level) too.

257
258 The concept of risk is defined by the CSE itself, and it is directly linked to the demand
259 (e.g. decrease the number of disease cases or deaths, decrease migrations flows, etc.). Given a
260 level of hazard and a level of vulnerability of the CSE, a decrease of the exposure or sensitivity of
261 the elements of the ecosystem, or an increase of their capacity to adapt will significantly reduce the
262 risk of the ecosystem. This dynamic concept of value, risk and resilience implies that there could
263 be multiple ways for a CSE to change over time based on the state conditions, demand, time, stake-

264 holders, climate services and interactions of the network. Unfortunately, the amount of resources
265 are limited and the dynamics of the CSE are also impacted by budget constraints. The proposed
266 approach supports the value-analysis of different scenarios, allowing decision-makers to as-
267 sess which is the most Pareto-efficient option (or set of options) given the existing budget constraints.

268

269 **3. A hybrid framework to analyse climate services ecosystems**

270 Given the definition and the characteristics of the CSEs mentioned in the section above, it is
271 essential to have both qualitative and quantitative tools to analyse climate services ecosystems, their
272 context, characteristics, structure and evolution. A qualitative analysis of an ecosystem requires
273 the analysis of the decision-making context of the actors involved. The required approaches and
274 tools to analyze the context have already been discussed extensively in the literature (e.g. Goddard
275 et al. 2014; Goddard 2016; Visscher et al. 2019; Goddard et al. 2020; Bojovic et al. 2021; Baulenas
276 et al. 2023; Terrado et al. 2023b,a, , and references therein). Hence, this section focuses on two
277 related quantitative approaches that complement the qualitative contextual analysis: Network
278 Analysis and Dynamical Bayesian Network Analysis.

279

280 Network Analysis (for a recent review see Kirschbaum 2019) intuitively comes as an ap-
281 proach when dealing with climate services ecosystems. This approach helps to identify patterns
282 within CSEs, helping to better understand which actors and services are involved, how they are
283 connected, and how the information flows in the ecosystem. Network Analysis can also help
284 compare different CSEs, although with some restrictions -e.g. the compared networks should have
285 similar characteristics, such as for example the size of the CSE.

286

287 This type of analysis supports the understanding of connectivity among the nodes, and the
288 dynamics of the CSEs in relation to potential modifications of the nodes (e.g. involved actors)
289 and the structure of the network. In other words, Network Analysis is a useful tool to quickly
290 summarise (or take a snapshot at a particular moment in time of) key aspects of the climate
291 services ecosystem from a topological or network theory point of view. However, as it has been
292 pointed out in the specialised literature (see Kirschbaum 2019, and references therein), Network

293 Analysis has limitations when analysing the temporal evolution of the network or when dealing
294 with attribution analyses. For example, it is possible to identify through a Network Analysis a
295 certain change in a given CSE (e.g. an increase of the scope of a climate service), but the approach
296 has limitations identifying whether that change is produced by a given project, program, budget
297 change, an institutional arrangement or a combination of all.

298

299 To study the temporal evolution of the CSE and attribution of changes in the dynamics of
300 CSEs, the paper proposes the use of a Dynamical Bayesian Network Analysis, which allows to
301 explore causation and (re-)assess the value of the CSE for a given shock (e.g. budget changes,
302 merges or divisions of institutions, program implementation, etc.). The following subsections
303 provide details on each one of these methods.

304 *a. Network Analysis*

308 Network Analysis is commonly used in a variety of fields, from medicine, biology, and social
309 studies to financial analysis (e.g. Chen et al. 2012; Tajbakhsh et al. 2016; Zhang and Horvath 2005;
310 Kleindorfer et al. 2009). This type of analysis focuses on understanding how the combination of
311 individual elements can create enduring, functioning networks (Borgatti et al. 2009). It looks at
312 kinship patterns, community structures and overall relational information (Scott 2017), seeking to
313 uncover various kinds of patterns and to determine the conditions under which those patterns arise
314 and what they imply for the network (Freeman 2004).

315

316

317 Following the Social Network Analysis approach (a variety of Network Analysis, e.g. Scott
318 and Carrington 2014), in CSEs, information of interest can be drawn from climate services
319 as individual nodes, and also sets of nodes part of the ecosystem. This approach avoids the
320 consideration of climate services as independent silos, and promotes the analysis of CSEs
321 considering the implications of the climate services participating on it.

322

323 As a simple example of the type of outcomes provided by a Network Analysis in this context,
324 consider the question of what is the most efficient network configuration to communicate climate

305 FIG. 4. Different network connectivity examples: (a) regular lattice network, (b) small-world network, (c)
306 Erdős-Rényi random network, and (d) real-world climate services ecosystem (data from the ACToday project,
307 Central America region). For details see main text and Table 1.

325 information produced by a climate service ecosystem: how the different institutions should
326 be interconnected? The average path length, or how many "steps" on average can any node
327 reach another node (a metric for connectivity) is a measure of efficiency of the transmission of
328 information: the lower the value, the more efficient the transmission is.

329

330 In this example (see Figure 4), a 170-node CSE network identified in Central America by
331 the Columbia World's Project "ACToday" (ColumbiaWorldProjects 2021) is compared against
332 three different network configurations: a regular lattice (Figure 4a) consisting of each node only
333 connected to near-neighbour nodes, a random network (Erdős-Rényi network, Figure 4b), with

345 TABLE 1. Average path length, indicating how many steps on average can any node reach another node (a
 346 metric for connectivity), for each network exhibited in Figure 4.

Panel	Network	Average path length (L)
(a)	Regular lattice	14.586
(b)	Erdős-Rényi (random)	0.663
(c)	Small world ($\beta = 5$ Watts-Strogatz model)	3.154
(d)	CSE in Central America	2.601

344 completely random connections between nodes, and a small-world network (Figure 4c, defined
 345 as a $\beta = 5$ Watts-Strogatz model, (Watts and Strogatz 1998)). The Network Analysis conducted
 346 here shows that the Central America CSE under study is topologically equivalent to a small-world
 347 network, due to their comparatively smaller *average path length* (Table 1), which is a common
 348 metric to quantify the structural properties of networks (several other metrics can be used for
 349 different purposes in this regard, depending on the concrete attributes to analyze). The analysis
 350 suggests that CSE networks with high average path lengths compared with small-world networks
 351 should be re-wired (the institutional interconnections should be re-planned) in order to be more
 352 efficient in terms of communicating information produced by their climate services. Hence,
 353 Network Analysis offers ways to quantify theoretical optimal values related with different network
 354 configurations, that can be potentially translated into real-world recommendations for CSE.

347 Natural sciences have traditionally critiqued social network research due to its descriptive analysis
 348 and the lack of comparison with expected values from theoretical models (Borgatti et al. 2009).
 349 However, the use of Social Network Analysis for climate services ecosystems can provide value
 350 information on:

- 351 • CSE typologies. Understanding how elements affect and interact with each other, looking for
 352 types of CSE based on similarities, relationships, interactions, and information flows.
- 353 • CSEs' structures, properties analysis and node outcomes based on the position of the elements.
- 354 • Centrality analysis to understand the importance of a node in the CSE network.
- 355 • Mechanisms to explain the consequences of the direct transmission of information between
 356 nodes within a CSE. The adaptation mechanism could explain how elements of the CSE
 357 become homogeneous as a result to adapt to a similar environments. The binding mechanism,
 358 on the other hand, aims to explain how environmental elements or ties can bind nodes together

359 as to build a new node with different characteristics from its parents. The exclusion mechanism
360 analysis the power dynamic existing in a given ecosystem.

- 361 • Estimation of past and future changes of a CSE. Associations among nodes can be inferred,
362 allowing for the estimation of probabilities of past and future events (Pearl 2010) or changes
363 of the CSE, if the conditions remains the same. These association analysis can be defined in
364 terms of a joint distribution of observed variables (Pearl 2010).

365 *b. Dynamical Bayesian Network Analysis*

368 Bayesian Network Analysis is proposed here as a complementary tool, as it aims at inferring
369 probabilities under changing conditions, like changes induced by programs, policies, budgets,
370 institutional changes or any other external interventions. The causal assumptions that can be
371 inferred from Bayesian Network Analysis identify relationships that remain invariant when
372 external conditions change, allowing for the assessment of these changes, predictions of plausible
373 scenarios and evaluation of counter-factuals and testable scenarios (Pearl 2009). The assessment
374 of causality derived from a Bayesian Network Analysis implies that the influence of one event
375 onto another is stable and autonomous, so the change in one of them would necessarily result on a
376 change in the linked event.

377
378 Applying these ideas to CSEs, changes in one climate service will likely influence other
379 climate services linked to the former. Bayesian Network Analysis combines graphs, probabil-
380 ity and statistical modeling, allowing for the representation and analysis of the response and
381 changes of the CSE to external or spontaneous changes (Pearl 2009), like the ones mentioned before.

382
383 The time sensitivity of a CSE, as described in Section 2, may require the use of Dynami-
384 cal Causal Network Theory to model the relationship between the nodes, or climate services,
385 of a CSE. A dynamical analysis brings the opportunity to model both time-dependent and
386 time-independent nodes, if timing is a necessarily element for any of the nodes of the CSE. A CSE
387 model may contain multiple variables representing different but (potentially) related time series.
388 Their dependencies can be modeled leading to representations that can take multivariate time
389 series predictions. This means that instead of using only a single time series to make a prediction,

366 TABLE 2. Table with an example of the explanation of variables for a simplified CSE for health and agriculture.

367 U_n represents the errors due to omitted factors and random errors.

Sector	Node	Function	Description
Climate	X_1	$X_1 = f_1(\text{seasonal model output}, U_1)$	Seasonal forecast system for precipitation
Climate	X_2	$X_2 = f_2(\text{subseasonal model output}, U_2)$	Subseasonal forecast system for precipitation
Health	X_3	$X_3 = f_3(X_1, X_2, U_3)$	Dengue forecast system
Health	X_4	$X_4 = f_4(\text{socioecon data}, U_4)$	Socioeconomic index or data
Health	X_5	$X_5 = f_5(X_3, X_4, U_5)$	Early Warning System (EWS)
Health	X_6	$X_6 = f_6(X_5, U_6)$	Action-based protocol
Health	X_7	$X_7 = f_7(X_5, U_7)$	Climate and health bulletin
Agriculture	X_8	$X_8 = f_8(X_1, X_2, U_8)$	Index-based insurance

390 multiple time series and their interrelations can be utilised to make better predictions and analyses.
 391 The approach is illustrated in the following paragraphs.

392
 393 In a CSE, the nodes can take discrete, continuous or multi-variable values, allowing for
 394 the analysis of different elements or characteristics in a CSE. A Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG), a
 395 graph with directed links and no directed cycles, represents a CSE as a system of processes and
 396 provide a causal interpretation of the changes within the network or system.

397
 398 Figure 5 illustrates a simplified version of a CSE that involves three sectors, i.e. climate,
 399 health and agriculture, and eight different climate services (or nodes). Here, the combination
 400 of longer-term outlooks for precipitation (X_1 , e.g. seasonal forecasts) and shorter ones (X_2 ,
 401 subseasonal forecasts) allows to put information into context (Goddard et al. 2014) for other
 402 climate services like a dengue forecast system (X_3) and an index-based insurance product (X_8).
 403 The dengue forecast system feeds into an Early Warning System (EWS) for vector-borne diseases
 404 (X_5), that unfolds into an action-based protocol (X_6) and a climate and health bulletin (X_7). Table
 405 2 summarizes the sectors, variables (here nodes of the Bayesian network), and a description of the
 406 variables and functions that define each node.

407
 408
 409 Following Pearl (2009), here it is proposed to use a structural equation model (SEM) approach to

Fig. 5. Example of a simplified CSE involving health and agriculture. See Figure 5 and main text for details.

410 mathematically define each node, such that:

$$x_i = \sum_{k=1} \alpha_{ik} x_k + u_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

411 where the α_{ik} are regression coefficients of the model, u_n represents realizations of both random
 412 errors and the errors or disturbances due to omitted factors. The lower case symbols (e.g. x_i, u_i)
 413 in this and the following equations just serve to remind that these are particular realizations of the
 414 corresponding variables (e.g. X_i, U_i).

415
 416 This approach allows to determine the value of each variable X_n . Applying the nonlinear,
 417 non parametric generalization of the linear SEMs, it is possible to write:

$$x_i = f_i(p a_i, u_i), \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

418 where pa_i represents a realization of the Markovian parents (PA_i) of x_i , and the value of x_i responds
419 to every possible value combination of pa_i, u_i .

420 The Markovian parents are the preceding variables that are sufficient for determining the proba-
421 bility of X_i , knowing the values of other preceding variables is redundant once we know the values
422 pa_i of the parents set PA_i (Pearl 2009). This concept is the essence to define the memory of the
423 system and, instead of specifying the probability of x_i conditional on all possible realizations of
424 its predecessors x_1, \dots, x_{i-1} , it is only need to specify the possible realizations of the set PA_i that
425 makes x_i dependent to pa_i (Pearl 2009), such that:

$$P(x_i, \dots, x_n) = \prod_i P(x_i | x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}), \quad (3)$$

426 and thus

$$P(x_i | x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}) = P(x_i | pa_i) \quad (4)$$

427 Putting this mathematical framework in the context of the example illustrated by Figure 5, the
428 lines connecting the different nodes represent the dependency between the variables. Figure 5
429 shows a dependency between the forecasts products, both at seasonal (x_1) and subseasonal level
430 (x_2), and the dengue forecast system (x_3) and the index-based insurance (x_8). The EWS (x_5),
431 the action-based protocol (x_6) and the climate and health bulletin (x_7) are screen off-ed from the
432 forecast systems described above by their Markovian parents (x_3 and x_8 , respectively).

433

434 Hence, an important conclusion is that the value of the overall ecosystem is primarily
435 based on the exchange value between Markovian-parent-related nodes. The higher the number of
436 these interactions, the higher the value of the CSE.

437 *c. Case study: How much those Priority Interventions cost? A cost assessment example*

438 Donors and decision makers normally need to have a cost assessment of adaptation plans.
439 Dynamic Bayesian Network Analysis can be used as a valuation modeling tool to assess the cost
440 of action plans targeting different expected climate and socio-economic conditions, informed by a
441 network (an ecosystem) of climate services.

442 To illustrate this particular application of Dynamic Bayesian Network Analysis in the context
443 of climate services ecosystems, consider the case of the Anticipatory Action Framework (AAF)
444 developed by the United Nations Office of Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) for
445 Guatemala ⁸, and consider a particular region there, located in the Central American Dry Corridor.
446 As described in the OCHA’s AAF, two seasonal forecast systems (the local one produced by
447 INSIVUMEH -the National Meteorological Service- and the one produced by the European Centre
448 for Medium-Range Forecasts -ECMWF) are used to trigger concrete Priority Interventions by
449 sector, including food security and health.

450 For the sake of simplicity, consider the ecosystem of services represented by the network shown
451 in Figure 6, involving the most updated socio-economic information for the target region, cli-
452 mate information -the latest observations and seasonal forecasts- and also dengue forecasts. A
453 probabilistic Early Warning System (EWS) is developed by combining expected conditions (in a
454 tercile-based probabilistic approach), as indicated by the arrows in Figure 6. This EWS triggers
455 concrete actions if dry conditions (Figure 6a) -such as a drought-, or very wet conditions (Figure 6b)
456 -such as a flood or crop-damaging intense rainfall- are expected. A high number of dengue cases
457 can be expected both during wet conditions, because rainfall tends to produce suitable habitats for
458 mosquito reproduction, and dry conditions, because humans tend to storage water during droughts,
459 also leading to suitable habitats for mosquito reproduction.

460 Knowing the base costs related to each component of the ecosystem and that of the Priority
461 Interventions, by changing only the probabilities related to dry (category 0) or wet (category 2)
462 conditions in the “ClimateInfo” node, and by using equation (4), a Dynamical Bayesian Network
463 can help identify the expected costs for dry and wet conditions, as well as many other configurations,
464 as discussed by (Muñoz et al. 2024).

473 **4. Discussions and concluding remarks**

474 *The main purpose of climate services is to respond to the demands of society by supporting*
475 *decision-making processes to adapt and mitigate the effects of a changing climate.* In the past
476 20 years, the climate services community has proliferated and evolved developing a wide and
477 complex arena, not yet capable of reaching its full potential (Cortekar et al. 2020). A lot of effort
478 has been put into developing climate services for long-term adaptation purposes, leaving shorter

⁸<https://www.unocha.org/publications/report/guatemala/anticipatory-action-framework-dry-corridor-guatemala>

465 FIG. 6. Example of the use of Dynamical Bayesian Networks to assess expected costs of a set of Priority
 466 Interventions and Anticipatory Actions (node: ActionPlanCost) under (a) dry and (b) wet conditions, related
 467 to a climate service ecosystem involving an Early Warning System (node: EWS) that uses socio-economic
 468 information (node: SocEcInfo), climate information (both observations and forecasts; node: ClimateInfo) and
 469 dengue forecasts (node: DengueForecasts), as indicated by the arrows. The expected costs are defined in terms
 470 of the probability density function seen in the final node, while each of the other nodes exhibit probabilities (the
 471 percentages indicated in each box) of below-, near-, and above-normal categories, represented by 0, 1 and 2 in
 472 the vertical axis, respectively. For details, see text.

479 terms overlooked (Nissan et al. 2019), and limiting the capacity of the society to adapt to a rapidly
 480 changing climate.

481
 482 It is still common to see climate services being developed with a focus on the supply-side and
 483 the academic perspective, rather than on the needs and requirements of the communities. These

484 perspectives bring important limitations to the value of the services and the tools developed.
485 For example, it is fairly common for climate services to be of no further use after their
486 conception-to-deployment phase because of a limited (or wrong) understanding of the demand
487 (making the climate service unfit for purpose), or because the deployments are requested by
488 donors and projects to happen in a specific time-frame, rather than responding to the pace of
489 the final users (Woltering et al. 2019). These supply-side perspectives eventually bring negative
490 return-to-investments in projects, as they leave unfit climate services, they erode the trust from
491 the general public, increasing the chances of failing for adaptation and mitigation strategies (and
492 thus the intrinsic value of the climate service itself) and, more importantly, leaving communities'
493 needs and demands unheard and invisibilised.

494
495 Most operational climate services remain part of the grey literature, making the under-
496 standing of the demand in a systematic way difficult. It also makes it difficult to assess the
497 commonalities that enable (or limit) the use of climate services. Nevertheless, and according to
498 the academic literature, there are several obstacles for societies to adapt to changes in climate at
499 long term and short term: inefficient use of climate information, lack of tailored services, data
500 constrains, uncertainty of data, models and information, communication issues, limited funding,
501 lack of monitoring and evaluation strategies, high costs of computing infrastructure, lack of
502 standardization and limited capacity to scale up- just to mention the most common ones (Tart et al.
503 2018; Lamich 2018; Lu et al. 2021).

504
505
506 The characterisation of climate services vary depending on several factors, like the existing
507 demand, the scale, the field, the location and the budget available, among others. However,
508 regardless of those characteristics, they are likely to be influenced by the interactions with many
509 other climate services, institutions and/or agents in that same (or different) scale, field, and
510 location. Climate services ecosystems bring the concept of natural ecosystems to the climate
511 services arena, serving as a way to assess how climate services interact among each other,
512 developing an opportunity for optimization of resources, scale assessments, and hence helping
513 increase the climate resilience of society and the value of the climate services.

514

515 The concept of climate services ecosystems brings a novel perspective of understanding
516 the realm of climate services in a integrative and unifying approach to optimize resources, support
517 upscaling and increase resilience, in a context of limited resources, changing needs and constant
518 shocks, completely aligned with the purposes of the World Meteorological Organisation’s Global
519 and National Framework for Climate Services. While there might be other perspectives to analyze
520 climate services ecosystems (e.g. a governance point of view), this paper presents the perspective
521 of optimization of resources and value assessment in a cohesive way, understanding the impact
522 of climate services in society from an connected system perspective rather than silos, offering
523 quantitative ways to identify and analyze these ecosystems. For this reason, the paper suggests
524 the use of Network Analysis and Dynamical Bayesian Network Analysis to analyze interactions
525 between the elements of a CSE and its value.

526

527 Moving from a silo-thinking to a CES approach when developing climate services could
528 help to understand how to assess and build the interdependency between the nodes to facilitate the
529 information flow, the orchestration of resources and scalability at a vertical (more users, sectors
530 and geographical domains), horizontal (creating institutional change and an external enabling
531 environment) and functional (new functions or elements to increase reach and impact) level
532 (Guentchev et al. 2023). This would require a significant amount of coordination and collaboration
533 among institutions and an enabling political sphere like the one described in GFCS or National
534 Adaptation Plans.

535

536 Budget constrains and donor requests to evaluate the impact of climate services related projects
537 have become significantly more common in the past years. Monitoring and evaluation strategies
538 of interventions tend to focus on the definition of different metrics for the outputs, outcomes and
539 impacts of a particular climate service or project. While some of these metrics are necessary to
540 respond to donors’ demands, they may lack a cohesive answer to the question: what is the overall
541 value of the climate service for a given society (or in a climate service ecosystem)? Traditional
542 monitoring and evaluation approaches lack the key consideration of the dynamics and interaction
543 between climate services. The ecosystem approach to climate services offer a complementary

544 way to assess the value of a collection of climate services interacting as part of the same network,
545 offering a more comprehensive way to assess the resilience and the capacity to adapt to a changing
546 climate. Indeed, the approaches discussed in this paper, in particular the use of Dynamical Bayesian
547 Network Analysis, can be further developed to help with economic assessments of climate services
548 and their integration in functioning ecosystems, which is a hot area of interest, especially to donors.

549

550 The authors propose the use of Network Analysis to compare CSE against typologies of
551 topological networks (in this example we used regular lattice network, Erdős-Rényi random
552 network and a small world network as comparisons, but there might be other types of topological
553 networks that can be compared to). This comparison helps to characterize the information flow
554 in CSE under analysis and to assess whether an improvement can be implemented regarding the
555 connection and interdependence of the nodes, enhancing the resilience of the CES. This analysis
556 allows to answer questions regarding the structure of the CSE. For example, what happens to the
557 CSE if one node, institution or climate service is removed from the CSE? How does that impact
558 the resilience of the CES? Does it mean that this particular node, institution or climate service is
559 of utmost importance for this CES? Which organization increases the connectivity flow between
560 the nodes, and thus, increase the resilience of the CSE? The answer to these questions could help
561 orchestrate resources among the CSE and support the scalability of CS from a functional, vertical
562 and horizontal point of view.

563

564 Additionally, the application of Dynamical Bayesian Network Analysis to CSE, can recre-
565 ate plausible scenarios of what is likely to happen to an ecosystem of climate services through the
566 implementation of the story telling approach. Dynamical Bayesian Network allows to perform
567 different types of analysis like: descriptive (e.g. to identify and describe patterns within and
568 across CSE); diagnostic (e.g. calculate the value of the ecosystem (through the assessment of its
569 information flow), causal (e.g. to establish causal-based optimization links between institutions
570 and climate services), predictive (e.g. what if scenarios) and prescriptive (e.g. evidence-based
571 optimization), which can support policy recommendations and decision making process under
572 uncertainty environments.

573

574

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581 **Data and Software Availability Statement**

582 Due to confidentiality agreements, supporting data can only be made available to researchers
583 upon request and subject to a non-disclosure agreement. Software code is available upon reasonable
584 request via the corresponding author.

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